

MODERN APPROACHES TO TEACHING RUSSIAN GRAMMAR

Nilufar Adkhamovna Usmonova

Instructor at Fergana State University, Fergana, Uzbekistan

Article information:

Manuscript received: 21 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Sep 2024; **Published:** 08 Oct 2024

Abstract: The article discusses modern approaches to teaching Russian grammar to students. It describes methods aimed at improving the understanding of grammar rules through contextual learning, communicative exercises, creativity, and interactive tasks. It also touches on approaches such as gamification of the learning process and the flipped classroom method. These techniques make grammar learning more engaging, practical, and motivating for students.

Keywords: Russian grammar, contextual learning, communicative approach, gamification, interactive exercises, creativity, media resources, flipped classroom method.

Studying grammar often evokes negative associations among students, as it is traditionally associated with memorizing rules and performing monotonous exercises. The many grammatical constructions, exceptions, and nuances characteristic of the Russian language may seem complex and overwhelming. As a result, many students lose motivation and feel that grammar has little connection to the real use of the language. However, modern approaches to grammar instruction are aimed at changing this perception. New methodologies emphasize the practical application of grammatical rules in real-life situations, making the process more logical and meaningful. Instead of memorizing grammatical structures in isolation from context, students are immersed in various linguistic scenarios where grammar functions as a natural tool for communication. By using digital technologies and gamification, learning becomes more interactive and engaging. Applications and online platforms allow students to practice grammar through games and quests, compete with peers, and receive instant feedback, which helps them absorb the rules gradually and effortlessly. Active use of media resources—such as podcasts, videos, movies, and music—also helps students intuitively perceive grammatical constructions and reinforce them through repetition. This is especially important because grammar in live speech is often used differently than in textbooks, and media resources provide better insight into real language practices. Modern approaches are transforming grammar instruction, making it not only more enjoyable but also more effective. They focus on helping students see grammar not just as a set of rules but as a means to achieve communication and express thoughts in the Russian language.

1. Contextual Learning

Contextual learning is considered one of the most successful methods, as it directly connects grammatical rules with real-life situations. Unlike the traditional approach, where students are asked to memorize rules in isolation, this method aims to integrate grammar into everyday scenarios, helping students understand and retain the material more quickly. The core idea of contextual learning is that grammatical constructions are naturally perceived by students during the execution of real communicative tasks. For example, when studying noun declensions, instead of mechanically memorizing endings in different cases, students may be presented with tasks that they are likely to encounter in real life. These could include giving directions to a certain place, making a shopping list, or filling out official documents or forms,

where correct word forms must be used in the appropriate contexts. In this way, the student masters the rules not at a theoretical level, but through practical application, which promotes better retention and understanding of the grammatical features of the language.

Another example might be dialogues. When discussing various topics, such as shopping, traveling, planning events, or describing a favorite hobby, students naturally use different grammatical constructions, such as verb tenses, cases, and prepositions. Classroom dialogues reflecting real communication situations help students apply grammar while interacting with their peers. This could involve role-playing scenarios where students discuss weekend plans or ask for assistance in a store. Such tasks not only help students learn grammatical structures but also promote the development of communication skills in Russian.

Contextual learning also stimulates cognitive processes involved in natural memory retention. Psychologically, when students see a connection between grammatical rules and their real lives, this creates associations and helps them remember and reproduce the rules more effectively. For instance, if a student describes their morning and uses verbs in the past tense, they form a concrete picture that reinforces the use of verbs in the correct form. This approach is more effective than memorizing abstract examples from a textbook, which may be quickly forgotten due to a lack of connection to reality. Contextual learning also opens up broad opportunities for creativity. Students can create their own stories, write essays, or compose dialogues where they must apply grammar in specific situations. This approach encourages active language use and helps learners feel more confident in applying grammatical rules in both speech and writing. Ultimately, contextual learning allows grammar to become a part of a living language rather than a dry theoretical discipline. This method helps students master Russian through practical situations, where grammar becomes a natural element of communication rather than a complex set of rules to memorize.

2. Communicative Approach

The communicative approach to teaching Russian grammar is one of the most modern and effective methods, aimed at developing the ability to use the language in real-life situations. Unlike traditional methods that emphasize memorizing rules and performing template-based exercises, the communicative approach focuses on helping students master the language as a tool for communication. This means that grammatical constructions are learned not in isolation but in the context of real speech, where the primary emphasis is on the meaning and functionality of the language. The main goal of the communicative approach is to teach students to express their thoughts, ideas, and emotions in Russian. This is achieved through tasks that simulate real communicative situations. For example, role-playing games are a powerful tool for developing grammar skills. These games may include situations that could arise in everyday life: ordering in a restaurant, booking a hotel, job interviews, conversations with friends, or discussing weekend plans. During these role-plays, students naturally apply grammatical constructions: verb tenses, prepositions, agreement of forms, and noun declensions. These exercises improve students' understanding of grammar in real speech, rather than as memorized material.

Writing assignments also play an important role in the communicative approach. For example, writing emails, social media messages, or keeping a personal diary in Russian all help to develop writing and grammar skills. When students write, they must consciously apply grammatical rules in accordance with what they want to express. Writing on various topics—from formal ones, such as requests to official institutions, to informal ones, such as letters to friends or social media posts—allows students to practice using different language styles and master diverse grammatical structures. A key feature of the communicative approach is its focus on the functions of grammar in speech. This means that students not only learn how to correctly construct sentences but also understand why and how to use certain grammatical constructions in different communicative contexts. For example, using the past tense when telling a story or using conditional mood in discussing hypothetical situations. The communicative approach also encourages collaboration and interaction among students. Many tasks require working in pairs or groups, where students interact with each other, discuss tasks, ask questions, and share their

opinions. This not only develops grammar skills but also improves overall communicative abilities. When students work together, they learn to negotiate, clarify their thoughts, and correct each other, which helps reinforce grammar rules through live communication. Another important aspect of the communicative approach is the continuous feedback from the teacher. The teacher acts as a facilitator, guiding students and correcting their mistakes without interrupting their natural communication. Instead of correcting every mistake the moment it occurs, the teacher may do this after the communicative task is completed, allowing students to focus on expressing their thoughts rather than constantly correcting errors. A significant advantage of the communicative approach is that it gradually reduces language barriers and the fear of making mistakes. Students begin to see grammar not as a complex system of rules that must be mechanically memorized but as a means of achieving their communicative goals. Ultimately, this helps them feel more confident and free when using Russian in real-life situations.

3. Grammar Through Creativity

Grammar through creativity is a method that significantly differs from traditional approaches to learning language rules. It is based on the idea that creative activity activates cognitive processes such as associative thinking, critical analysis, and creativity. This helps students not just memorize grammatical constructions but use them in a more flexible and lively manner. One of the key elements of this method is writing stories. When students write their own stories, they are not simply reproducing pre-made phrases but are constructing sentences themselves, which requires the practical use of grammar. For example, writing a short story requires students to carefully think through verb tenses to indicate past, present, or future actions, properly agree adjectives with nouns, and correctly apply case forms. Students are faced with the need to use different constructions depending on the nature of the story, whether it is describing actions, emotions, or dialogues between characters.

Blogging or keeping diaries in Russian is also an excellent way to integrate grammar through creativity. This format allows students to regularly practice writing texts on topics that interest them, which motivates them to use the language more frequently. When students write about events in their lives or reflect on various topics, they apply complex grammatical structures such as compound sentences, participial and adverbial participial constructions, which deepens their understanding and strengthens their command of the language. Another interesting creative tool is the creation of comics. This method is attractive to those who prefer visual expression of ideas and is especially effective when teaching teenagers or children. Creating comics requires not only visual creativity but also the construction of dialogues, descriptions, and character actions, which involves using different grammatical forms depending on the context. For instance, describing a character's actions requires correct use of verbs in different forms and tenses, while dialogues necessitate knowledge of syntax and agreement in speech.

The **grammar through creativity** method allows students to develop their language skills in a relaxed and inspiring atmosphere. Lessons become more engaging as students have the opportunity to express their thoughts and emotions through text or visual art. Creative assignments offer freedom of choice: students can choose a topic that interests them, which significantly boosts their motivation to learn. Through creative tasks, students begin to realize that grammar is not just a set of formulas and rules but a tool for expressing their ideas and communicating. Gradually, they start to better understand how various grammatical structures affect the meaning and tone of the text. For example, using different verb tenses conveys a sense of dynamism or sequence of events, while proper use of participles and adverbial participles makes the text richer and more expressive. The creative approach also fosters the development of analytical thinking: when creating a text, students learn to consciously select grammatical constructions, guided by the context, purpose, and style of their work. This method helps solidify the rules, as students apply them in practice and see the results of their efforts.

Ultimately, the **grammar through creativity** method makes language learning an enjoyable and multi-layered process. It helps students not only master grammatical rules but also develop creative thinking skills, which are extremely important in the modern world. Creative assignments provide a better

understanding of the language as a living, dynamic tool that can be used for various purposes, whether telling stories, expressing emotions, or describing reality.

4. Interactive Exercises and Applications

Interactive exercises and applications have become increasingly popular tools for learning grammar in today's educational landscape. Modern technologies offer a variety of platforms that make the learning process more engaging, effective, and accessible. These tools incorporate elements of gamification, turning learning into a game and encouraging students to engage regularly. One of the most well-known examples is the Duolingo app. This app offers exercises where users must choose the correct answers, construct sentences, and translate phrases. The tasks are broken down into small blocks, making the learning process gradual and manageable. In Duolingo, grammar rules are presented through practical exercises, allowing students to intuitively remember structures. For example, instead of memorizing a list of declensions or conjugations, students see them in real sentences and choose the correct forms. Progress is accompanied by instant feedback, which helps students quickly correct mistakes and better understand the material.

The Lingvist app also offers an innovative approach to grammar learning. It focuses on the repetition of words and grammatical constructions based on statistics. The app adapts to the student's level of knowledge, allowing them to focus on the aspects of the language that need extra attention. Lingvist uses scientific methods to create personalized drills, helping students memorize grammar in the context of relevant tasks. Skyeng is more than just an app; it is a comprehensive educational platform that offers both individual and group lessons with instructors. In addition, the platform contains a large number of interactive exercises that can be completed at any time. Students can practice grammar through games, quizzes, and other interactive tasks. For example, the exercises may be built around communication scenarios or specific tasks, such as writing messages, filling out forms, or participating in role-playing games. Skyeng also provides access to extensive databases of study materials, including video lessons and podcasts, which help students gain a deeper understanding of grammar topics. Memrise is another popular app that uses mnemonics to help students memorize words and grammar rules. Instead of simply memorizing rules, students associate new constructions with images or situations, which aids long-term retention. Memrise also incorporates gamification elements: students earn points as they complete exercises and can compete with other participants, making the learning process more engaging.

These platforms have several key advantages. First, they offer instant feedback, which is crucial for learning grammar. If a student makes a mistake, the app immediately corrects it and provides an explanation, helping the student to better understand the material. Second, interactive exercises adapt to the student's level of knowledge. They start with simple constructions and gradually become more complex as the student gains confidence in their skills. This prevents information overload and helps students gradually absorb grammar rules. Another important advantage of interactive applications is their accessibility. They allow students to study anywhere and anytime using a phone or computer. This is especially important for students with busy schedules, as they can dedicate just 10–15 minutes a day to exercises, helping to maintain consistency in their studies. Interactive exercises also make learning more visual. Many applications use animations, images, and videos, which help students absorb the material more easily. For example, in some applications, grammar rules are illustrated through visual metaphors or diagrams, which help students better understand their structure and logic. The use of interactive applications and online platforms opens up new horizons for learning Russian grammar. They make the learning process more interesting, dynamic, and results-oriented, helping students not only to better understand grammar but also to actively apply it in practice.

5. Gamification of the Learning Process

Gamification of the learning process is a powerful tool that makes grammar learning not only effective but also enjoyable. The application of game elements to education helps change students' attitudes toward learning, transforming it from a routine task into an engaging and motivating activity. The core of gamification lies in involving students through competition, rewards, and goal achievement, encouraging

them to learn more actively and consistently. One of the key elements of gamification is the **system of points and rewards**. Many apps and online platforms, such as Duolingo or Kahoot, offer students the opportunity to earn points for completing tasks and passing quizzes. Accumulated points allow students to track their progress and compete with others. Depending on the number of points, a student may receive virtual rewards, titles, or levels, which add extra motivation to complete exercises. For instance, completing a challenging grammar task correctly might earn a student a badge or the chance to move to the next level, which is associated with achieving a particular goal and sparks further interest in learning.

Competitions between students are another popular element of gamification, often used both in classrooms and online courses. These can be either team-based games or individual competitions where students race against each other in speed and accuracy while completing grammar exercises. For example, in applications like Quizlet or Kahoot, a teacher can organize quizzes based on grammar rules, and students compete to see who can answer the questions faster and more accurately. This element of competition motivates students to study harder and review the material to excel in the challenge. A crucial part of gamification is the **setting of clear goals and tasks** that need to be achieved. In gaming systems, students see their learning objectives as missions or quests that they must complete to progress further. For example, in grammar games, students might be given a "grammar quest" where each task requires them to correctly use specific grammatical constructions. Successfully completing each task leads to a reward or unlocking a new level.

Another interesting element of gamification is the **leaderboards**—tables of top performers that show which students have achieved the best results in the learning tasks. This fosters a sense of competitive spirit and encourages students to outperform their peers. Seeing their name at the top of the leaderboard gives students a sense of satisfaction and drives them to continue learning. It's important to ensure that such competitions remain friendly and supportive, rather than stressful, so that motivation doesn't turn into pressure. In addition to competitive elements, gamification also includes **softer forms of motivation**, such as personal achievements and individual progress. Many platforms offer users personalized goals that adapt to their level of knowledge and progress. For example, in Duolingo, students are given a daily task to complete a set number of exercises, earning "streaks" (consecutive days of completed tasks). This allows students to track their progress in real time and encourages them to maintain regular study habits.

Furthermore, gamification makes the learning process more **visual and emotionally engaging**. Game elements such as colorful animations, characters, sound effects, and visual rewards make the learning process more interactive and enjoyable. This helps to keep students' attention and makes grammar learning less monotonous. It's important to note that gamification is not just about entertainment; it's an effective pedagogical strategy. By engaging students in a game, it helps improve cognitive processes such as memory, attention, and logical thinking. Completing game-based tasks requires students to actively apply grammar rules, which contributes to better retention and reinforcement. Studies show that gamification can significantly increase student motivation and engagement in the learning process, leading to better academic outcomes. In the end, gamification of the grammar learning process helps students not only remember rules better but also enjoy the learning experience itself. With elements of competition, rewards, and visual support, it makes grammar less of a daunting and boring task, transforming it into an exciting adventure where every step leads to new success.

6. Flipped Classroom Method

The flipped classroom method is an innovative pedagogical approach that radically changes the traditional understanding of the learning process. Unlike conventional lessons, where theoretical material is studied during class and homework focuses on reinforcing it, the flipped classroom reverses this process: students study the theory at home, while class time is devoted to actively applying the knowledge. The main advantage of this method is that students can master theoretical material at their own pace, which is especially important when studying complex grammar topics. For example, when learning grammar theory at home, students can rewatch video lectures multiple times, pause at difficult points, take notes, and return to the material whenever necessary. This allows for a deeper understanding of the theory and

removes the pressure often felt in the classroom, where material must be quickly absorbed within limited time frames. When students come to class, all their energy is focused on actively applying what they have already studied at home. This allows class time to be used more productively, focusing on practice. In class, the teacher can organize practical exercises, discussions, or creative tasks that help reinforce the theory in real communicative situations. For example, instead of listening to an explanation of verb conjugation rules, students might use them in dialogues, participate in role-playing activities, or write short texts. Another important aspect of the flipped classroom method is that it allows teachers to devote more attention to the individual needs of students. Since the core theory has already been covered, the teacher can work on the aspects that are challenging for students and provide them with the necessary support. This creates a more flexible and supportive learning environment, where students can get answers to their questions and work on their weaker areas in grammar.

The format of the flipped classroom also encourages more active participation from students in the learning process. In class, they are not just passively listening to the teacher's explanations but actively engaging with the material. This could involve discussing grammar rules in the context of real-life situations, analyzing texts, or working collaboratively on projects. Such activities help students better understand how grammar is used in real life and apply their knowledge in various communicative tasks. One of the key aspects of the flipped classroom method is the development of students' independence and responsibility. Since much of the theoretical work is done at home, students learn to manage their time and take responsibility for mastering the material. This is important not only for the learning process but also for developing self-organization skills that will be valuable in the future. Additionally, the flipped classroom creates favorable conditions for the use of modern technologies in education. Video lessons, interactive presentations, online courses, and other digital resources become an integral part of the learning process. Students can access materials at any convenient time, making learning more flexible and convenient. This is particularly useful for those who need to review material or do extra preparation before class. In class, the focus is placed on collaborative work, discussions, and active learning methods. This can include solving grammar problems in groups, creating collective projects, or holding debates where students must apply the grammatical constructions they have learned. This approach makes learning more dynamic and interactive, which contributes to better retention of the material. The flipped classroom method offers a more effective way to master grammar, as students have the opportunity to study the theory at their own pace while actively applying their knowledge in practice during class. This approach promotes not only a better understanding of grammar rules but also the development of critical thinking, collaboration, and self-directed learning skills, making it relevant and valuable in modern education.

Modern approaches to teaching Russian grammar offer students a variety of methods and tools that make the learning process more effective, engaging, and practical. The use of contextual learning helps students better understand grammatical constructions by applying them in real-life situations, while the communicative approach develops the skills of live communication, where grammar becomes a tool for expressing thoughts. Creative tasks, such as writing stories or creating comics, turn grammar into a means of creative self-expression, while interactive exercises and applications provide flexible and accessible ways to practice rules in a game format. Gamification of the learning process stimulates students through competitions and rewards, making the learning experience more motivating and exciting. The flipped classroom method allows students to master theory at their own pace and then actively apply it during class, contributing to deeper retention of the material. The use of media resources such as films, podcasts, and songs helps students intuitively grasp grammatical constructions by immersing them in the linguistic and cultural environment. Each of these methods is designed to make learning grammar not only useful but also interesting. They help students move from mechanical memorization to meaningful use of the language in real-life situations. These approaches develop not only literacy but also confidence in using the Russian language, making it a part of everyday communication and creative expression. Ultimately, such methods help students not just learn grammatical rules but also gain a deeper understanding of the language as a living and dynamic tool for communication.

References

1. Bim, I. L. *Theory and Practice of Teaching Russian as a Foreign Language* / I. L. Bim. — Moscow: Russian Language, 2010. — 320 p.
2. Galskova, N. D., Gez, N. I. *Theory of Teaching Foreign Languages: Linguodidactics and Methodology* / N. D. Galskova, N. I. Gez. — Moscow: Academia, 2006. — 400 p.
3. Solovova, E. N. *Methodology of Teaching Foreign Languages: Basic Course of Lectures* / E. N. Solovova. — Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 2008. — 336 p.
4. Savinkova, L. G. *Methodology of Teaching Russian as a Foreign Language in the Context of Modern Educational Technologies* / L. G. Savinkova. — St. Petersburg: St. Petersburg State University, 2014. — 254 p.